

Incidental Cerebral Microbleeds: Correlation with Risk Factors and Regional Distribution in a Young and Middle-aged PopulationSachin Khanduri¹, Zaara Khan², Surbhi³, Rohit⁴, Avani Kanojia⁵¹Head of Department, Radiodiagnosis, Era Lucknow Medical College and Hospital²Junior Resident, Radiodiagnosis, Era Lucknow Medical College and Hospital³Senior Resident, Radiodiagnosis, Era Lucknow Medical College and Hospital⁴Junior Resident, Radiodiagnosis, Era Lucknow Medical College and Hospital⁵Junior Resident, Radiodiagnosis, Era Lucknow Medical College and Hospital

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Abstract:**Background:** Incidental cerebral microbleeds (CMBs) are asymptomatic brain hemorrhages detected via MRI, linked to various cerebrovascular risk factors. This study investigates the correlation between CMBs and risk factors such as hypertension, smoking, diabetes, hyperlipidemia, alcohol consumption, and family history in a young and middle-aged population aged 18-50 years, along with their regional distribution.**Methods:** A retrospective cohort study was conducted with 200 participants aged 18-50 years, selected between May 2022 and December 2023. Participants with positive MRI findings for CMBs underwent detailed risk factor analysis, including age, gender, hypertension, diabetes, smoking, previous stroke history, medication usage, and family history. The regional distribution of microbleeds in deep, lobar, or both locations was also assessed.**Results:** The prevalence of CMB was highest in the 40-50 age group, followed by the 30-39 group, and then the 18-29 group. There was a significant male predominance, with a larger proportion of males affected compared to females. Risk factors included hypertension (43.5%), smoking (63.5%), diabetes (23%), hyperlipidemia (31.5%), and alcohol consumption (27%), while 12% had no risk factors. CMBs were found in both deep and lobar regions in the majority (63% of cases), followed by the deep or lobar region alone. Additionally, some individuals had a history of stroke, a history of drug use, and a positive family history.**Conclusion:** This study highlights significant correlations between incidental CMBs and common risk factors in a young population. The high prevalence among smokers and hypertensive individuals, along with a notable male predominance, underscores the need for early risk factor management to mitigate CMB impact. Further research should explore additional factors contributing to CMBs, especially in those without conventional risk factors.**Keywords:** Cerebral Microbleeds; Risk Factors; Young Population; Magnetic Resonance Imaging; Retrospective Cohort Study; Regional Distribution.

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Introduction

Cerebral microbleeds (CMBs) are hypointense lesions observed on T2*-weighted gradient echo MRI, potentially indicative of past microhemorrhages [1]. Their prognosis is not fully understood, but clinical studies suggest that CMBs might predict future stroke risk [2,3]. Cross-sectional studies have explored the prevalence and determinants of microbleeds in patients with stroke and the general elderly population [4-7].

The reported prevalence of CMBs varies across studies due to differences in MRI techniques. However, overall findings indicate a high prevalence of CMBs among stroke patients and the elderly, increasing with age. Consistent risk factors

include age and hypertension, with markers of cerebral small vessel disease also showing significant relationships. Additionally, the spatial distribution of CMBs may indicate specific vascular pathologies, such as cerebral amyloid angiopathy or hypertensive vasculopathy [8].

Hypertensive arteriolosclerosis and cerebral amyloid angiopathy contribute to 78–88% of primary intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH) cases [9]. Smaller, potentially subclinical hemorrhages may precede symptomatic ICH. These lesions, known as cerebral microbleeds, may signal an increased risk for future macroscopic hemorrhages [10,11].

Microbleeds are also linked to ischemic stroke (IS), Alzheimer's disease (AD), and AD immunotherapy [12-15]. They show an age-dependent higher prevalence in cognitively normal elderly individuals [16,17]. Furthermore, they can occur secondary to trauma, inflammatory conditions, and genetic disorders [18,19].

Methods:

The study was carried out at the Department of Radiodiagnosis in collaboration with the Department of Medicine at Era's Lucknow Medical College & Hospital, Lucknow. Clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee of Era's Medical College (Approval number: ELMC & H /RCELL, EC/2021/162), and informed consent was obtained from all patients.

Participant Selection: A cohort of 200 young participants aged 18-50 years was retrospectively selected from May 2022 to December 2023. Participants were chosen based on positive MRI findings for incidental CMBs detected using a Magnetom Vida 3 Tesla MRI machine.

Data Collection: Data on demographic details, along with presenting complaints, medical history, past and drug history were obtained through clinical examinations and patient records. Risk factors including age, gender, hypertension, diabetes, smoking, previous stroke history, and medication usage were analyzed.

The regional distribution of microbleeds was examined in deep, lobar, or both locations.

All MRI images were post-processed using Syngo.via software for three-material decompositions.

Statistical Analysis: The study performed descriptive statistical analysis to identify the prevalence of risk factors and the distribution of CMBs among participants.

Results:

The results indicate a significant association between incidental CMBs and several common risk factors in a young population. The majority of CMB cases were observed in the 40-50 years age group (55%), followed by the 30-39 years group (28%), and the least in the 18-29 years group (16.6%). A marked male predominance was noted in 78% of the cases, compared to 22% of females.

The prevalence of risk factors among participants with CMBs:

- Smoking: 63.5%
- Hypertension: 43.5%
- Diabetes: 23%
- Hyperlipidemia: 31.5%
- Alcohol consumption: 27%
- No identifiable risk factors: 12%

The regional distribution of microbleeds showed a significant occurrence in both deep and lobar regions (63%), followed by deep regions alone (28%), and lobar regions alone (9%). Additionally, 16% of participants had a history of previous stroke, 46% had a drug history, and 24% had a positive family history. Please see the table below for detailed demographic data.

Table 1: Age of the Participants.

Age in Years	No. of patients	Percentage
18-29	33	16.65%
30-39	57	28.50%
40-50	110	55.00%
Total	200	100

Table 2: Sex Profile of the Participants.

Gender	No. of patients	Percentage
Male	156	78.00%
Female	44	22.00%

Table 3: Distribution of Risk Factors

Risk Factors	No. of patients	Percentage
Hypertension	87	43.50%
Smoking	127	63.50%
Diabetes	46	23.00%
Hyperlipidaemias	63	31.50%
Alcohol	54	27.00%
Normal	24	12.00%
Total	200	100.00%

Table 4: Clinical profile of the participants

		No. of patients	Percentage
Past History of Stroke	Yes	30	15.0%
	No	170	85.0%
Drug History	Yes	92	46.0%
	No	108	54.0%
Family History	Yes	48	24.0%
	No	152	76.0%

Table 5: Regional distribution of bleeds

Region	No. of patients	Percentage
Lobar	18	9.00%
Deep	56	28.00%
Both	126	63.00%

Figure 1: 45-year-old male with tingling, numbness, and impaired memory with a positive history of hypertension and diabetes. Transaxial scan shows multiple tiny blooming foci on SWI in both lobar and deep regions including brainstem and basal ganglia along with diffuse cerebral atrophy and ischemic demyelination.

Figure 2: 39-year-old male with slurring of speech and left sided hemiparesis with a previous history of stroke. Transaxial scan shows multiple tiny blooming foci on SWI predominantly at cerebral grey-white matter junction with additional chronic lacunar infarcts in right corona radiata.

Figure 3: 48-year-old male with headache with a long history of hypertension and smoking. Transaxial scan shows multiple tiny blooming foci on SWI in both lobar and deep regions including a few large focal hemorrhages in right temporal and occipital lobe.

Figure 4: 25-year-old male with tension-type headache with no significant past history. Transaxial scan shows single tiny blooming focus on SWI in left corona radiata.

Figure 5: 32-year-old female with fatigue with a past history of hyperlipidaemia and hypothyroidism compliant with her medications for the past 2 years. Transaxial scan shows multiple tiny blooming foci on SWI predominantly at cerebral grey-white matter junction involving only lobar region.

Discussion:

This study provides valuable insights into the correlation between incidental cerebral microbleeds (CMBs) and various cerebrovascular risk factors in a young population aged 18-50 years. Our findings underscore the significance of common risk factors such as hypertension, smoking, diabetes, and hyperlipidemia in the prevalence of CMBs,

alongside an intriguing analysis of the regional distribution of these microbleeds.

Comparison with Literature: Our data demonstrate a strong association between CMBs and smoking, with 63.5% of participants who had CMBs reporting a smoking history. This finding aligns with existing literature indicating that smoking exacerbates vascular injury and microbleed formation through mechanisms such as

increased oxidative stress and inflammation. For example, Vernooij et al. (2008) also identified smoking as a significant risk factor for CMBs in their population-based study [5]. Hypertension was the second most prevalent risk factor, present in 43.5% of the CMB-positive participants. This is consistent with the Framingham study by Jeerakathil et al. (2004), which highlighted hypertension as a primary risk factor for CMBs [7]. Hypertension is well-documented to cause small vessel disease, manifesting as CMBs on MRI. Diabetes and hyperlipidemia were also significantly associated with the presence of CMBs, observed in 23% and 31.5% of participants, respectively. These findings are supported by the AGES-Reykjavik study, which suggested that metabolic conditions contribute to endothelial dysfunction and atherosclerosis leading to microbleeds [4].

Interestingly, 12% of participants with CMBs had no identifiable risk factors, suggesting that other factors, potentially genetic or environmental, might play a role. This contrasts with findings from older populations, where traditional risk factors like hypertension and diabetes are more predominant. Further research is essential to elucidate these additional risk factors in younger cohorts.

Regional Distribution of CMBs: The regional distribution of CMBs in our study revealed a significant occurrence in both deep and lobar regions (63%). This differs from studies in older populations, such as those by Greenberg et al. (2009), where lobar microbleeds are typically more common due to underlying pathologies like cerebral amyloid angiopathy [8]. This could reflect different underlying pathophysiologies in a younger demographic, potentially influenced by distinct risk factor profiles.

Gender and Age Distribution: A notable male predominance (78%) in CMB cases was observed, which can be attributed to higher prevalence rates of smoking and hypertension among young men compared to women in our study population. This gender disparity emphasizes the need for targeted preventive measures and lifestyle modifications, particularly among young men at risk of developing CMBs.

The age distribution showed a higher prevalence of CMBs in the 40-50 years age group, suggesting that the cumulative effect of risk factors over time may play a crucial role in the development of CMBs. This trend underscores the importance of early intervention and sustained risk factor management from a younger age to prevent cerebrovascular complications later in life.

Clinical Implications and Future Directions: Our findings have important clinical implications, particularly for the early detection and management

of cerebrovascular risk factors in young adults. Regular screening for hypertension, diabetes, hyperlipidemia, and smoking cessation programs should be emphasized to mitigate the risk of CMBs and related complications.

Furthermore, the presence of CMBs, even in the absence of traditional risk factors, highlights the need for broader diagnostic approaches, possibly including genetic and advanced imaging studies, to identify other contributing factors. Longitudinal studies are warranted to assess the progression of CMBs and their potential impact on cognitive function and stroke risk in young populations.

Limitations: This study has several limitations. As a retrospective cohort study, it may be subject to selection bias and is limited by the accuracy of recorded data. The sample size, though robust, still represents a relatively small population. Additionally, the study does not account for potential confounding factors such as socioeconomic status, diet, or physical activity levels, which might influence the prevalence of CMBs. Future research, should aim to address these limitations and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the mechanisms underlying CMBs.

Conclusion

This study highlights the correlation between incidental cerebral microbleeds and various risk factors in a young and middle-aged population. The findings suggest that smoking and hypertension are major contributors to the occurrence of CMBs. The data also reveal a significant gender disparity and age-related prevalence.

Further research is needed to explore underlying mechanisms and additional risk factors, particularly in patients without conventional risk factors. Early detection and management of identified risk factors may help mitigate the impact of CMBs on cerebrovascular health.

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